

Utilizing Artificial Intelligence in Prosthodontics: Advancements, Applications, and Future Directions

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the capacity of machines to execute actions typically demanding human cognitive abilities. In the contemporary epoch, it is a transformative, data-centric technology. It is bringing about a paradigm shift across a multitude of sectors, ranging from space science to the field of dentistry, engendering profound advancements. This study reviews the utilization of AI in prosthodontics. Prosthodontics, primarily focuses on the restoration and rehabilitation of missing teeth through the use of fixed and removable prostheses or biocompatible alternatives such as implants. In the realm of Prosthodontics,

Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a pivotal role by aiding in prosthesis design, functional maxillofacial appliance creation, treatment planning, diagnosis, patient documentation and overall patient management. This technology enhances the efficiency of dental healthcare professionals.

The subsequent review underscores the current state of AI technology in dental prosthetics and its effectiveness in enhancing patient-specific prosthesis, diagnosis and fabrication. In summary, AI exhibits a dual nature in dentistry, encompassing both potential applications and limitations.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, digitization, prosthodontics, innovation, dentistry, AI

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the theory and development of computer systems capable of performing tasks that historically required human intelligence, such as recognizing speech, making decisions, and identifying patterns.⁽¹⁾

The coinage "artificial intelligence" was initially introduced by John McCarthy in 1955. Regarded as the progenitor of artificial intelligence, McCarthy was a luminary in the field of mathematics.⁽²⁾

Artificial intelligence pertains for the capacity of machines to replicate human cognition and actions.⁽²⁾ With the proliferation of electronic devices facilitating various aspects of human life, the data they capture enables facile utilization and analysis through artificial intelligence (AI). AI is experiencing exponential growth and dissemination across all sectors including robotics, automotive technology, urban planning for smart cities, and financial analytics, among others, enabled by its capacity to assimilate human knowledge and execute tasks traditionally necessitating human intelligence⁽³⁾

The realm of artificial intelligence has significantly transformed both medicine and dentistry across various fronts. Beyond conventional disease diagnosis relying on singular information sources targeting specific ailments, AI exhibits the capacity to assimilate insights from multiple modalities (multi-modal data), surpassing human diagnostic capabilities.⁽³⁾ Notably, AI-driven image-based analyses have proven robust and efficacious. These advancements hinge upon the

swift evolution of computing process that is hardware, algorithmic innovations that is software, and the availability of expansive datasets (input data).⁽³⁾

Numerous ongoing studies and implementations are exploring the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in dentistry across various domains including diagnosis, decision-making, treatment planning, prediction of treatment outcomes, and disease prognosis. These applications can be categorized into four main areas: diagnostics, decision-making support, treatment planning assistance, and prediction of treatment results. Among these, diagnostic applications are particularly popular, with AI enabling more precise and effective diagnoses, thereby potentially reducing the workload of dentists. AI research in dentistry spans all areas of the field, reflecting its comprehensive engagement and potential impact.⁽³⁾

AI IN PROSTHODONTICS

Prosthodontics is the dental specialty pertaining to the diagnosis, treatment planning, rehabilitation, and maintenance of the oral function, comfort, appearance, and health of patients with clinical conditions associated with missing or deficient teeth and/or maxillofacial tissues by using biocompatible substitutes.⁽⁴⁾

Prosthodontics primarily focuses on the diagnosis, treatment, and crafting of both removable and fixed dental prostheses, alongside expertise in implant surgery and the creation of maxillofacial prostheses. Moreover, it encompasses the meticulous preparation of finishing margins adjacent to teeth to enhance the extension and fit of prosthetic devices. Furthermore, prosthodontics is instrumental in preserving optimal maxillomandibular relationships and selecting appropriate tooth coloration for aesthetic enhancement.⁽⁵⁾

The fabrication of dental prostheses holds significant importance for several reasons. Firstly, the absence of tooth structure can lead to compromises in physical, mental, and emotional well-being. This deficiency affects chewing capabilities (mastication), ultimately influencing an individual's dietary habits. Secondly, the lack of teeth can induce feelings of isolation due to concerns about social acceptance. Since proper aesthetics, including teeth and associated soft tissue, are integral to social interaction, their absence may hinder socializing. Lastly, the presence of teeth within the oral cavity contributes to maintaining proper tongue position and the placement of lips and cheeks, thereby preserving the appropriate shape of facial structures.⁽⁵⁾

AI holds significant promise in aiding various therapeutic treatment plans. In Prosthodontics, where both patients and clinicians demand gold standard quality in prosthetic outcomes, a vast array of human resources and machinery is typically employed to achieve perfection. However, reliance solely on manpower may occasionally fall short of expectations. To streamline the process and conserve time and energy, computer-aided designing and manufacturing units have been developed.⁽⁶⁾ These technologies enable the customization of prostheses through digital design and fabrication, catering to the specific desires of individual patients. AI can be quite beneficial in a variety of therapy protocols.^(5,6)

Computer-Aided Design/Computer-Aided Manufacturing

Computer-aided design/computer-aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM) is increasingly prevalent in prosthetic dentistry, with AI integration bolstering chair-side utilization. This technology encompasses a computerized design and manufacturing unit facilitating customized milling or printing based on patient preferences, thus optimizing time and energy resources.⁽⁷⁾

CAD/CAM systems typically generate two- and three-dimensional models, which are subsequently materialized via numerically controlled mechanics. This method facilitates the scanning of prepared teeth and the fabrication of restorations from ceramic blocks, simplifying prosthetic repairs by eliminating casting processes. Moreover, CAD/CAM technology is instrumental in producing inlays, onlays, crowns, and bridges, supplanting traditional casting procedures and reducing the likelihood of human error in the final prosthesis.⁽⁸⁾

Dentists leverage AI to craft visually pleasing prostheses tailored to individual patients, accounting for factors such as facial proportions, ethnicity, anthropological considerations, and patient preferences.⁽⁹⁾ Various CAD/CAM techniques, including additive manufacturing and subtractive milling (e.g., 3D printing), are employed to fabricate prostheses, enhancing both functionality and aesthetics with precise restoration design and milling.⁽⁸⁾

The application of AI and CAD/CAM in removable denture design and production elevates denture quality while optimizing laboratory workflows by minimizing manual processes. Intraoral scanning technologies, extending beyond radiology, enable detailed examination of intraoral scans using dental inspection software. This software empowers clinicians to assess their images, receive immediate feedback on preparations, and facilitates laboratories in analysing scans to assess dental professionals' performance and provide tailored training as needed. Automated margin marking ensures precise preparation scans for milling and digital

design, while AI-driven programs can streamline the design of single posterior crowns in the laboratory.⁽⁸⁾

Tooth-Supported Fixed and Removable Prosthesis

AI in Removable Dental Prosthesis

A less invasive and cost-effective alternative for replacing missing teeth is the utilization of removable partial dentures (RPDs), supported either by adjacent teeth or implants. The meticulous design of RPD components stands as a pivotal stage in prosthesis fabrication. The advent of AI algorithms has significantly enhanced RPD design processes.⁽⁸⁾ AI can be integrated into the fabrication of RPDs via 3D printing technology, where software applications can provide RPD design recommendations tailored to partial edentulism. Leveraging 3D printing technology streamlines RPD fabrication, offering heightened efficiency, precision, and cost-effectiveness compared to conventional methods. Moreover, AI algorithms contribute to the development of personalized RPD designs by analysing patient-specific data and anatomical considerations. Additionally, AI can play a role in evaluating RPD fit and functionality. Computer-assisted analysis of RPD fit provides precise measurements and assessments of occlusion and overall function, facilitating the identification and resolution of any issues with the prosthesis. This comprehensive approach enhances patient satisfaction and outcomes by ensuring optimal RPD performance and fit.⁽¹⁰⁾

AI in Fixed Dental Prosthesis

In fixed prosthodontics, the original tooth structure of a dental prosthesis undergoes scanning, followed by software-based assessment to recommend various courses of action.⁽⁸⁾ Synthetic intelligence systems are currently under development for application in fixed prosthodontics. These systems rely on a vast database of millions of dentist-approved crowns, continuously updated to the cloud, serving as the foundation for AI's analytical and learning capabilities. Utilizing this database, the computer evaluates the construction of high-performance restorations to ascertain the ideal occlusion, contacts, and margins for each case, thereby learning from successful crown designs. Traditionally, dentists manually prepared tooth margins using handpieces and various burs during the creation of fixed dental prostheses. Optimal contour and extension of marginal lines surrounding teeth were crucial to maintaining the prosthesis in place and ensuring a healthy environment for the gums and periodontium. However, these techniques required considerable time and technical expertise. The aim was to mitigate errors and reduce the labour-intensive nature of manual procedures.⁽⁹⁾

Zhang et al.⁽¹¹⁾ conducted research on deep learning (DL) models to accurately extract marginal lines. This study involved 380 dental preparation models, employing a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model called Sparse Octree (S-Octree) for data retrieval. Through the dental preparation process, a sparse point cloud with labels was generated, and an eight-depth octree structure was developed for analysis.⁽¹¹⁾ Training, validation, and testing datasets were established, and CNN models were trained by assigning labels to dental preparations. Back-projection and boundary extraction methods were utilized to extract a tooth preparation line in the study, resulting in an average precision of 97.43%. This heightened accuracy demonstrates AI's potential to rectify human errors, positioning it as a viable alternative in dental practice.⁽¹¹⁾

AI in Aesthetic Dentistry

Designing an aesthetically pleasing smile in dentistry necessitates the digitization and integration of data to formulate a comprehensive diagnosis and a virtual simulation of the expected outcomes. Previewing clinical results before initiating therapeutic procedures is crucial in the decision-making process, as it enhances predictability and improves communication among the dentist, dental laboratory technician, and patient.⁽¹²⁾ Virtual smile design software enables dental professionals to customize various aspects of a patient's smile, including tooth shape, size, colour, and position. This level of customization ensures that the resulting smile harmonizes with the patient's facial features and personality.⁽¹²⁾

Initially, the patient's anatomical structures are converted into digital data, which can be managed and exported. Intraoral and extraoral scanning files are then merged using advanced software programs and existing knowledge. This approach leverages computer-aided design (CAD) and computer-aided manufacturing (CAM) technologies to perform complex, multi-faceted treatments effectively.⁽¹²⁾

Implantology

Artificial intelligence (AI) has been leveraged to enhance the precision of implant placement and planning through the analysis of cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) images and the construction of three-dimensional models of patients' jawbones. This technology aids in determining the optimal location and angulation for implants, thereby increasing the success rate of the procedure.⁽¹³⁾ AI algorithms are also employed to evaluate bone quality and quantity, which are critical factors for successful implantation. By utilizing AI for CBCT image analysis,

clinicians can achieve more accurate measurements and identify areas with potential bone loss or pathology.⁽¹³⁾

Additionally, AI is used in implant dentistry to forecast implant stability and success rates by analysing patient data and variables such as bone density, implant length, and diameter. These predictive capabilities enable clinicians to make more informed decisions during implant planning and offer patients more accurate prognoses regarding treatment outcomes.⁽¹⁴⁾ The integration of AI in implant dentistry has the potential to significantly enhance treatment planning, implant placement, and overall success rates. By analysing patient-specific data and imaging, AI provides clinicians with valuable insights to optimize treatment outcomes. Nonetheless, it is crucial to recognize that AI should serve as an adjunct to, rather than a substitute for, the expertise and decision-making of human clinicians.⁽²⁾

The integration of digital technology into implantology has significantly transformed the discipline, enabling precise planning and placement of implants, as well as the design and fabrication of prostheses. Digital planning software permits clinicians to develop a virtual surgical guide that assists in the accurate positioning of implants during surgery. Subsequently, rapid prototyping technology can be utilized to produce the physical surgical guide, ensuring precise implant placement during the procedure. This method enhances accuracy and precision in implant placement, thereby minimizing the risk of complications and increasing the overall success rate of the procedure. Consequently, the application of digital technology in implantology and prosthodontics has revolutionized the field, offering enhanced precision, accuracy, and customization in treatment planning and execution.⁽¹⁵⁾

In a study conducted by Lee et al.⁽¹⁶⁾, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) based on AI were employed to categorize implants using panoramic and periapical radiography. The study concluded that the AI-CNN system's performance in categorizing implant procedures is nearly equivalent to that of human experts.⁽¹⁶⁾ Furthermore, Takahashi et al.⁽¹⁷⁾ conducted an extensive investigation to develop an AI framework for classifying dental arches, utilizing CNNs to assist in denture production. The training dataset was categorized using methodologies for computer-based autonomous learning, demonstrating the potential of AI in enhancing various aspects of dental implantology.⁽¹⁷⁾

Several challenges can arise when conventional CAD/CAM techniques are employed for cementing implant prostheses. These issues may include incorrect positioning, improper

cementation, and inaccuracies in occlusal or interproximal adjustments with an abutment.⁽¹⁰⁾ To address these problems, Lerner et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ introduced an AI model designed to minimize such errors. This AI model aids in the development of fixed implant prostheses with monolithic zirconia crowns by identifying abutment subgingival margins. Furthermore, it enables dental surgeons to focus on tooth preparation while maintaining proper interproximal and occlusal contacts. The primary objective of this AI model is to reduce errors and decrease wait times, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency and accuracy of the procedure.⁽¹⁸⁾

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in implant dentistry has significantly enhanced the accuracy and efficiency of surgical planning by enabling the synthesis of various scans and data types to formulate individualized treatment plans for patients. This advancement improves the likelihood of successful implant procedures and enhances patient outcomes.⁽¹⁰⁾

Predictive AI models are particularly useful in two key areas of dental implantology.

The first area involves predicting clinical outcomes using machine learning algorithms. For instance, a recurrent artificial neural network (ANN) optimized with memetic search can simultaneously analyse patient data, implant systems, and surgical techniques to predict success rates with an accuracy of 99.2%.^(19,20)

The second area utilizes AI to forecast the mechanical properties of bioimplant systems, thereby reducing the computational costs associated with optimizing implant design variables. Despite these advancements, further research is required to advance AI in the risk optimization of bioimplants.^(19,20)

Maxillofacial Prostheses

Maxillofacial prosthesis rehabilitation is integral for restoring function and appearance in patients with facial deformities or injuries resulting from hereditary diseases, cancer, or trauma. Such conditions often necessitate high-quality prosthetic treatment due to associated aesthetic and psychological challenges. Maxillofacial prosthodontists offer patients a variety of options for prosthetic rehabilitation to improve both function and appearance, thereby alleviating anxiety and enhancing quality of life without resorting to surgical interventions.⁽⁶⁾

AI has emerged as a significant contributor to the field of maxillofacial prosthodontics. Utilizing convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to simulate human neurons, AI facilitates the

design and production of maxillofacial prostheses, as well as digital planning and placement of extraoral implants. Prior to CAD/CAM technology, skilled manual carving of wax casts is necessary to reconstruct facial forms with maxillofacial prostheses.

AI-powered prosthetic devices offer innovative solutions for patients with maxillofacial abnormalities or injuries, addressing both functional and aesthetic concerns. For instance, AI-powered prosthetic eyes can restore vision without surgery, while smart reading glasses equipped with voice-activated technology aid visually impaired individuals in reading and facial recognition. Additionally, AI-driven tissue engineering has advanced the development of skin replacements for wound regeneration, offering temporary or long-term solutions to promote healing and prevent infections.

Artificial olfaction, a field of interest for decades, has been revolutionized by AI. Electronic nose models replicate the human olfactory system using various electronic sensors, enabling applications in disease diagnosis, environmental monitoring, public safety, food industry, and agriculture.⁽⁶⁾

In the fabrication of maxillofacial prostheses with CAD/CAM technology, the treatment process typically involves imaging methods (e.g., MRI, CT) to capture soft and hard tissue features. Computer software converts this data into rapid prototyping (RP) models, which are then transferred to wax casts for final adjustments.⁽⁶⁾ Silicone elastomer prostheses are typically constructed based on these casts. For cases requiring immediate prosthetic solutions, such as nasal deformities, computerized libraries can provide pre-designed forms for expedited fabrication, reducing overall treatment time compared to conventional methods.^(21,22)

LIMITATIONS

Artificial Intelligence (AI) facilitates the derivation of logical and realistic conclusions, thereby enhancing diagnostic accuracy. Despite its benefits, the application of AI in dentistry presents several challenges, including system complexity, the need for specialized expertise, and significant initial costs. AI systems are heavily reliant on datasets, which are typically used for both training and testing, potentially leading to data snooping bias. To ensure robust model training, these datasets must be meticulously classified and filtered.⁽²³⁾

Currently, the medical sector is advancing towards digitalizing diagnostics and reports, yet substantial progress is still required to obtain accurate data suitable for model training.⁽²³⁾ The incorporation of AI in prosthodontics also introduces ethical concerns. Issues such as patient

confidentiality and privacy, as well as the ethical ramifications of AI-generated diagnoses and treatment plans, must be addressed. There is a risk of AI systems being programmed with biases, resulting in discriminatory or unjust outcomes. Additionally, the potential displacement of dental technicians due to AI automation is a significant concern.⁽¹⁰⁾

To mitigate these issues, dental professionals must remain cognizant of the limitations and potential biases inherent in AI technology. It is crucial to utilize high-quality data and to ensure that algorithms undergo regular monitoring and updates. Furthermore, establishing ethical guidelines and regulations is essential to ensure the responsible and beneficial use of AI in dentistry.⁽¹⁰⁾

FUTURE SCOPE

The future of AI in dentistry appears highly promising. AI has the potential to significantly enhance diagnostic accuracy, assist in treatment planning, and improve the precision of prosthetic design, thus revolutionizing the dental field.⁽¹⁰⁾ The implementation of AI introduces decentralization in treatment processes, enabling medical professionals to conduct remote treatments more effectively. As AI continues to evolve, the accuracy of diagnosis of disease is expected to improve, with AI predictions complementing human diagnoses to enhance diagnostic precision.⁽²³⁾

However, it is crucial to address ethical concerns, such as data privacy and algorithmic fairness. Dental practitioners must possess a fundamental understanding of AI technology to ensure its proper and ethical use. As AI-based services proliferate in the market, it is essential for dental professionals to stay informed about the latest advancements to select the most appropriate AI services and enhance the patient experience.⁽¹⁰⁾

CONCLUSION

The field of artificial intelligence (AI) has significantly transformed medicine and dentistry.⁽²⁾ AI holds substantial potential to revolutionize dentistry by enhancing diagnostic accuracy, optimizing treatment planning, refining prosthetic design, and improving patient experiences.⁽²⁾

A review of current trends indicates that the use of AI in prosthodontics is increasing exponentially, often yielding results that match or surpass human performance. AI proves useful in various aspects, such as classifying denture fixtures, accurately extracting marginal

lines, and reducing human error in implant cementation.⁽²³⁾ Despite its advantages, it is crucial to remember that these technological advancements are rooted in human innovation and discovery. AI can support clinicians in performing tasks with greater precision but cannot replace human knowledge, skill, and treatment planning.⁽²⁾

Ethical considerations, including data privacy, informed consent, safety, transparency, and algorithmic fairness, must be addressed to fully leverage AI's benefits in healthcare. AI should be seen as an auxiliary tool that aids dental surgeons in their professional duties rather than a substitute for human expertise. As AI technology continues to advance, it is essential to prioritize human interests while enhancing AI's capacity to manage large datasets. With careful design and extensive clinical validation, AI can become an unbiased, reproducible, user-friendly, and transparent aid for dental practitioners. By incorporating AI into a multidisciplinary approach, researchers and clinicians can improve both oral and overall health outcomes for patients.⁽¹⁰⁾

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